

ISSUES OF DEVELOPMENT OF VALEOLOGICAL CULTURE IN
FUTURE PHYSICAL CULTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract. This article describes the content of the concepts of valeology, culture, and valeological culture. Also, the issues of developing valeological culture among future physical culture teachers were discussed in detail.

Key words: valeology, culture, valeological culture, lifestyle, hygienic education, health care.

Under innovative changes in the education system in the world, health pedagogy (health care) aimed at protecting human health is rapidly developing. The physical and mental health and well-being of the population determines the level of civilization of the state and shows the indicator of the nation's sustainable development. In this place, the formation of thinking and need for health protection in a person becomes important, and the scope of research that serves to ensure pedagogical efficiency in health infrastructures in the society is observed.

Issues of healthy lifestyle and hygienic upbringing, family upbringing were thoroughly researched in the research works of O. Musurmonova, D. Sharipova, M. Mahmudova, S.R.Mukhamediyeva, F.Abdurahimova, T. Ulmatkulov. Researchers from the countries of the independent commonwealth, such as IYAbrosimova, M.Z.Zangiyeva, YE.A.Mensh, VGPautov, EIPodnebesnaya, TVKamenskaya, AFGiorgievsky, etc., devoted themselves to the pedagogical aspects and problems of forming a healthy lifestyle and valeological culture in young people and conducted scientific research.

In the research works of foreign scientists such as R.Banton, G.Macdonald, K.Tons, S.Tilfold, A.Skriven, S.Garmann, the issues of human health protection, health values and development of valeological culture were researched.

Protecting the health of the young generation and the entire nation is an important issue in our country's transition to a market economy, building a free, democratic society, renewing the spirit of society, and promoting a healthy lifestyle in order to achieve high results in the spheres of state and social construction. has been studied as Based on the comments recorded in historical sources, we can come to the following conclusion:

- ensuring protection of human life and health has been recognized as one of the urgent social issues in all periods of human society. In the available sources, the factors that pose a serious threat to human life and health are indicated, and in most places, information is also provided about ways to eliminate these factors;

- in the resources created within the framework of the problem, among the factors that harm human life and health, the following can be indicated;

-poor sanitary conditions of the environment, non-observance of basic hygiene requirements, consumption of alcohol, non-exercise of the body through physical labor, non-observance of proper nutrition rules, and between a man and a woman who are considered mutually unfriendly committed adultery;

- in all sources, the occurrence of the above-mentioned situations by people harms the content of social relations, causes various diseases that endanger the human race and health, and members of the society are encouraged to unite for the development of the society.

Valeology takes into account the level of resistance of the human body to certain diseases and the presence of a strong defense in the body. At the same time, the "internal doctor" is the main physiological effect that ensures the recovery of the body when it is infected with a certain disease.

MX Egamberdiyev "Valeology" science in the educational-methodical complex, "The demand for modern human health conditions is very high, because the development of civilization, especially the development of new complex technologies, has changed the living conditions of a person. However, despite this, the formation of a science that studies human health on a deeper scientific basis has become a vital necessity [2].

In this regard, historical scientific data, life experiences of Eastern thinkers, European Union, Russian scientists, their scientific approach to the idea of health raised the need for further scientific study of human health, practical problems related to health, and as a result, today health is fundamental. A new science - the science of valeology - was formed to study its essence and its scientific foundations in a comprehensive manner.

The first founder of the creation of the science of valeology (1980) is the Russian scientist I.I. Brekhman [1], who suggested that the science be called "Valeology". Valeology is derived from the Greek word valeo, which means health, be healthy, and logos, which means learning, science [1].

The subject of valeological research is individual human health, its mechanisms and their management.

The object of valeology is people in the health zone. In other words, we consider the object of valeology to be almost a healthy person and a person who has fallen into a pre-pain state.

– Valeology analyzes individual health as a separate medical and social group, the essence of which can be characterized using qualitative and quantitative indicators.

– The goal of valeology is to understand the inherited mechanisms and reserves of a person's vital activity, to support his adaptation to external and working environment conditions at a high level.

– The main tasks of valeology:

– Quantitative evaluation and study of human health and its resources;

– Creating devices focused on a healthy lifestyle;

– Strengthening and maintaining human health by introducing a healthy lifestyle[5].

Valeology also deals with teaching and health, educational and educational issues. Valeology develops health care methods, prevents diseases. The main methods of studying valeology are health level diagnosis, prediction and individual health management.

In the scientific literature, the concept of "culture" is expressed as a multifaceted, multifaceted phenomenon (A.I.Arnoldov, L.M.Arkhangel'sky, V.I.Bakshantovskiy, B.S.Bratus, S.N.Ikonnikov, D.M.Stankov, A.I.Titarenko, A.K.Uledov, etc.)[4].

The authors emphasize the multi-functionality of culture, highlight its social nature, humanistic orientation. The following types of culture are analyzed: organizational culture (R. Lavl), innovative culture (VIDolgova), informational culture (YPMelenteva), psychological culture (NTSeleznyova), as well as thinking culture (OSAnisimov).

The definition that allows for a broad understanding of culture is its encyclopedic definition: Culture (lat. cultura - cultivation, upbringing, education, development, honoring) - development of society, human creative forces and opportunities is a certain level of development expressed in the types and forms of organization of people's life and activities, in their mutual relations, as well as in the material and spiritual values created by them.

The concept of "culture" is used to describe certain historical periods, certain societies, nations and peoples, as well as specific spheres of activity and life (labor culture, political culture); and in a relatively narrow sense - the sphere of people's spiritual life. It includes the object-related results of human

activity (machines, constructions, cognitive results, works of art, moral and legal standards, etc.), as well as during activity (knowledge, skills, abilities, intellectual level, spiritual and aesthetic development, worldview, forms and methods of human communication) covers human power and capabilities. It can be seen that culture is a characteristic of a person, both activity and personality. It reflects the level of a person's thinking and attitude towards himself [3] .

"Culture is what people produce and how they produce it." At the same time, production means the total human activity, which is the socio-cultural activity of people. In other words, culture consists in mastering the logical laws of the description of the results of perception as the norms of organizing the apparatus of the imagination. A number of authors study the general aspects of the culture of a certain group of people.

Y.N.Bogdanov distinguishes scientific and everyday use of the term "culture".

Daily meaning - always assessor; scientific meaning - refers to the essence that encompasses the evaluative approach to culture as one of the cases of scientific acquisition of the subject of activity. Culture is formed on the basis of the use of special means of education and training, being oriented towards a specific goal. On the other hand, it is the result of self-education, self-creation, which shows the social maturity of a person, his ability to solve issues important for himself and society.

Culture (culture), embodied in the forms of individual experience, represents the mutual harmony of knowledge and thinking, the culture of creative action, the culture of emotions, communication, and behavior as a kind of commonality.

As a subject of culture, a person is distinguished by his social stability, effective participation in social and professional life, and psychological compatibility. Thus, in order to successfully enter the culture, a person must find his place in it, determine the system of his interactions with the culture[3, 678] . The above serves as a basis for clarifying the concept of culture.

Culture is a system of activity norms created on the basis of spiritual, value and intellectual aspects.

The emergence of objective and subjective factors that threaten human life and their preservation to a certain extent means that an unhealthy environment has been established in society. As a result of the establishment of an unhealthy environment, the following situations arise: spiritual values (in particular, the sanctity of land, air and water, the health of the offspring, ensuring the stability

of peace in society, working to improve the material well-being of the population, the priority of mutual kindness among people, etc.) decrease in the level of importance; These include the increase of various diseases among people, the decrease in the body's work activity, the increasing mental stress, and others. The situations mentioned above have a negative impact on the cultural and economic development of the society.

The establishment of a culture of healthy living in the society is related to the level of skills of the members of this society regarding the culture of healthy living. Development of valeological culture among citizens, especially among future physical culture teachers studying in higher educational institutions, is one of the most important issues today. In recent years, in the field of pedagogy, resources have been created that talk about the actions being taken to create a culture of healthy life among society, in particular, among its citizens. In the research conducted by scientists such as A. Abidov, Y. Alisitson, A.V. Martonenko and Y.V. Novikov, the opinion is put forward that it is important to promote the culture of healthy lifestyle among students and to form their skills to follow the culture of healthy lifestyle. .

the opinion of the physiologist B.N. develop recommendations about not giving in and proper rest.

Nowadays, the lifestyle does not require a person to be overly active. The level of mobility of students, specialists engaged in mental work and representatives of the field requiring light physical work is sharply decreasing. Analyzing the essence of the daily routine typical of the members of the majority of the population, we can see that they do not have a serious physical load. For example, very little physical activity is observed in future physical culture teachers.

One of the main factors of valeological culture is the importance of proper and high-quality nutrition and strict adherence to hygienic requirements in the process of eating, it is recommended in the research conducted by YAAfanasev and Yakulikov.

In his book "The Secret of Health and Beauty", A.A. Agafonov expressed his views on rational nutrition and its importance in ensuring human health, and the scientist explains the cases of "improper rational nutrition" as follows: eating at any time to eat the period between meals is too long; eating too little or too much; constantly eating the same food; lack of vitamins in food; swallowing food without chewing it well.

The researches of pedagogues and physiologists B. Atoyev, R.I.Vorobyov and V.A.Dadash highlight the importance of dietary rules, general nutrition culture and its importance in determining a healthy lifestyle.

It is important to inculcate in the minds of students the need to achieve the purity of the environment and its protection in the formation of a healthy lifestyle culture.

Environmental protection in the researches of L.A.Alibekov, P.Baratov, S.M.Grombakh, E.O.Turdikulov, Sh.Qurbanov, Sh.Avazov, A.Ikromov, B.Holliyev, A.STokhtayev, Y.Shodimetov on the problems of organizing ecological education organization, content of relations between nature and man, creation of ecological education system; The form, methods and tools of ecological education, as well as environmental issues, as well as various spaces, conditions, and the basics of subjects, were analyzed.

"Ecological Education Concept" was presented by the scientists of our republic, E.O.Turdigulov, while Sh. Gurbanov's work analyzed the stress situations caused by the violation of psychohygiene requirements, which are considered an important factor of healthy living culture. Although a lot of work has been done in the meantime, future physical education teachers have enough understanding of environmental protection and the impact of environmental conditions on human health, especially on lifestyle. because it is not, it is appropriate to continue scientific research in the direction in question.

In most studies, one of the foundations of a healthy lifestyle is personal hygiene and the conditions for its observance, the essence of hygienic education organized among teenagers, the importance of organizing the personal hygiene of teenage (adolescent) girls and boys. its specific aspects are studied in detail. In the work of D. Kholikov, one of the important problems facing the science of pedagogy is the formation of a healthy culture of life in students, the role of the family in this process, preparation of adolescents for family life based on national traditions, and detailed information about sexual education. information is provided. Such information is effective in strengthening the negative views of future physical culture teachers on harmful habits. Another bad habit is drinking alcohol. Several works have been carried out in this regard. However, this evil is still having a negative impact on the society. The student's interest in drinking, as well as the insufficient understanding of the harmful consequences of this condition, lead to him developing such a habit as a result of consumption.

Today, even though valuable ideas and recommendations are being developed by our scientists regarding the problems of drug addiction and AIDS disease, it is spreading rapidly as a plague of our century. In the researches of scientists such as FSSodikov, O. Hasanov, N. Begjanov, Z. Ilyosova, I.K.Toporov, TOnqboyev, prevention and treatment of injuries occurring in the household, industrial enterprise, street or at home, as well as to the injured person First medical aid and its rules will be discussed.

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